

THE CLASSIFICATIONS OF LANGUAGE LEARNING AND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION IN DEVELOPED EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

¹Murodullayeva S.Y., ²Musayeva Hadicha Sherzod qizi, ²Hakimova Gulnoza Izzatillo qizi,

²Sharipova Dilobar Shuhrat qizi, ²Toxtaboyeva Asal Davronbek qizi

¹Scientific adviser, ²Students ff NSU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17824759>

This article explores the distinctions between language acquisition and language learning in a developed educational environment. It highlights how natural communication plays a vital role in language acquisition, especially among children, who absorb language effortlessly through interaction and exposure rather than formal instruction. In contrast, adult learners are often subjected to grammar-based and repetitive methods that neglect communication and hinder natural acquisition. The paper emphasizes the importance of communicative approaches in both first and second language development, suggesting that meaningful interaction remains the key to successful language mastery.

В статье рассматриваются различия между овладением языком и изучением языка в современной образовательной среде. Подчеркивается, что естественное общение играет решающую роль в процессе усвоения языка, особенно у детей, которые приобретают языковые навыки через взаимодействие и языковую среду, а не через систематическое обучение. Взрослые учащиеся, напротив, часто сталкиваются с грамматически ориентированными методиками, лишёнными живого общения. Автор отмечает важность коммуникативного подхода как в освоении родного, так и второго языка, где смысловое взаимодействие является основным условием успешного владения языком.

Maqolada rivojlangan ta'lim muhitida tilni o'zlashtirish (acquisition) va tilni o'rganish (learning) o'rtasidagi farqlar tahlil qilinadi. Unda tabiiy muloqotning tilni egallash jarayonidagi o'rni alohida ta'kidlanadi. Bolalar tildan ongli o'rganishsiz, atrof-muhit va muloqot orqali tabiiy ravishda foydalanishni o'rganadilar. Kattalarda esa grammatika va takrorlashga asoslangan usullar ko'p hollarda muloqotdan uzoqlashishga olib keladi. Muallif tilni samarali o'zlashtirishda kommunikativ yondashuvning muhimligini, ya'ni mazmunli muloqot tilni mukammal bilishga kalit ekanini ta'kidlaydi.

In order to acquire language, learners need a source of natural communication. Unfortunately, with adult students, a quick look at current methodologies clearly shows that communication is set aside, neglected or even disregarded. According to linguists, there is an important distinction between language acquisition and language learning.

As you may well have noticed, children acquire their mother tongue through interaction with their parents and the environment that surrounds them. Their need to communicate paves the way for language acquisition to take place. As experts suggest, there is an innate capacity in every human being to acquire language.

By the time a child is five years old, s/he can express ideas clearly and almost perfectly from the point of view of language and grammar. Although parents never sit with children to explain to them the workings of the language, their utterances show a superb command of intricate rules and patterns that would drive an adult crazy if s/he tried to memorise them and use them accurately. This suggests that it is through exposure to the language and meaningful communication that a first language is acquired, without the need of systematic studies of any kind. When it comes to second language learning in children, you will notice that this happens almost identically to their first language acquisition. And even teachers focus more on the communicative aspect of the language rather than on just rules and patterns for the children to repeat and memorise¹. In order to acquire language, the learner needs a source of natural communication. The emphasis is on the text of communication and not on the form. Young students who are in the process of acquiring a second language get plenty of “on the job” practice. They readily acquire the language to communicate with classmates.

In short, we see this tendency in which second language teachers are quite aware of the importance of communication in young learners and their inability to memorize rules consciously (although they will definitely acquire them through a hands-on approach just as they did with their mother tongue).

Unfortunately, when it comes to adult students, a quick look at the current methodologies and language courses available clearly shows that communication is set aside, neglected or even disregarded. In almost all cases, courses revolve around grammar, patterns, repetitions, drillings and rote memorization without even a human interlocutor to interact with. The very same courses that promise you language independence and the ability to communicate upon completion of the courses do NOT offer you a single chance to engage in meaningful conversations. How many times have you bought or read about “the ultimate language course” in which the learner simply has to sit in front of a screen to listen to and repeat words and phrases time and again. That is not communication. That is the way you train a parrot! The animal will definitely learn and repeat a few phrases and amuse you and your friends, but it will never ever be able to communicate effectively².

How could you be expected to communicate if you are never given the chance to speak with a real person? Language without real communication is as useless as Saint Valentine’s Day without lovers or Children’s Day without kids.

In some other scenarios, in which there is a teacher, the work done in class is mostly grammatically oriented: tenses, rules, multiple choice exercises, and so on and so forth. Is this similar to the way in which a child “acquires a language?” Definitely not. No wonder why so many people fail in acquiring a second language naturally. Simply because whatever they are doing is highly unnatural and devoid of meaning to them. This is the field of language learning. Language learning as seen today is not communicative. It is the result of direct instruction in the rules of language. And it certainly is not an age-appropriate activity for your young learners – as it is not for adults either. In language learning, students have conscious knowledge of the new language and can talk about that knowledge.

¹ <https://interoncof.com>

² <https://www.eslbase.com>